

PSYCHOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PERIOD BEFORE HIGHER EDUCATION IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Annotatsiya: Maqolamizda pedagogik metodlarning o`ziga xos xususiyatlari, dars jarayonida til o`rganishga doir o`yinlarning roli, guruh a`zolarining ishtiroki, o`yinlarning samarali olib borilishi, chet tilini o`rganishni kichik yoshdagi o`quvchilarda rivojlantirish, o`qituvchi va o`quvchi o`rtasidagi munosabatlarni mustahkamlash, muloqotning ko`pqirali va psixologik tomonlari haqida so`z boradi.

**Kalit so`zlar:** chet tili darslarida so`z o`yinlari, o`quvchilar ongli faoliyatini faollashuvi, xulosa qilish qobliyatini, kichik yoshdagi o`quvchilar ruhiyatini, che tili darslarida muloqot jarayoni.

Annotation: In our article, the peculiarities of pedagogical methods, the role of language learning games in the course of the lesson, the participation of group members, the effective conduct of games, the development of foreign language learning in young students, the teacher and strengthening of student-student relations, multifaceted and psychological aspects of communication are discussed.

Keywords: word games in foreign language classes, activation of students' conscious activity, ability to conclude, the mentality of young students, communication process in foreign language classes.

Аннотация: В нашей статье особенности педагогических методов, роль игр для обучения языку в ходе урока, участие членов группы, эффективное проведение игр, развитие обучения иностранному языку у младших школьников, учителя и обсуждаются вопросы укрепления студенческих отношений, многоплановые и психологические аспекты общения.

Ключевые слова: словесные игры на занятиях по иностранному языку, активизация сознательной деятельности учащихся, умение делать выводы, психика младших школьников, процесс общения на занятиях по иностранному языку.

Based on the content of education expressed in textbooks and manuals in the conditions of general education schools, it is permissible to highlight three main and important tasks of communication: teaching, educating, and developing tasks. Didactic games play an important role in performing these tasks. The organization of didactic word games in the lesson and its successful

implementation play an important role in activating the conscious activity of students, as a means of thorough acquisition of knowledge, and also serve to increase students' interest in a foreign language, their team forms and develops the qualities of working together, being friendly, concentrating, and strengthening memory. During the lesson, didactic games educate students' ability to hear speech in a foreign language, draw conclusions from it, and increase students' speech culture¹.

American psychologist D. Mead says that a person begins to work based on his inner "I" from childhood. We can determine the level of this "I" concept by the child's interest in various games. There is a concept of "play therapy" in medicine and psychology. The essence of this concept is that there is an opportunity to see the human psyche through games, which no other equipment in the world can reveal.

In teaching a foreign language, the game performs the following methodological tasks:

- mentally prepares children for the process of communication; - ensures multifaceted and effective communication;
- teaches to use the correct words in the process of communication;
- ensures that the child grows dexterous and agile.

The role of interactive games in the teaching process is very important. For example, organizing a lesson interactively, on the one hand, ensures the participation of the whole group, and on the other hand, it creates competition. The competition requires striving for a goal. Using different games in the lesson allows you to repeat a new topic several times.

But some scientists do not have a positive opinion about the role of the game in the lesson. That is, a lot of time is lost in the lesson through the game, and another disadvantage is that not all students accept it equally. However, under any circumstances, it is impossible to fully deliver the same lesson and new topic to all students. The main importance of the game during the lesson is not to bore the children and to inculcate a new concept in their brains without their knowledge. The effective conduct of games depends on the teacher. Here we turn to the following idea:

“Agar o'qituvchi tartibli bo'lmasa va dars berishga chinakam tayyor bo'lmasa, ularning o'quvchilari buni darhol qabul qiladilar: uzoq pauzalar va

qo'llarni tirnash, sinf tezligini sekinlashtiradi va o'quvchining o'quv jarayoniga bo'lgan ishonchini susaytiradi.²

That is, if the teacher does not organize the lesson properly, if the students encounter pauses during the lesson, their level of learning will decrease and their confidence in the lesson will be lost. We can take this situation as an example for students. Although they have not yet developed confidence, they see defects in the teacher's work and cannot fully feel the importance of science. Then the student starts to cool down from this subject. Especially, such defects in the process of teaching a foreign language can cause great difficulties later.

If the student does not understand one topic, it will be very difficult for him to learn the next one. For this reason, more repetition exercises are conducted in elementary school students. Because they suddenly have a slow understanding. Academician of International Pedagogy and Special Sciences N.N. Azizkhoyeva highly evaluates the use of game technologies in classes and emphasizes the following: "Psychological mechanisms of game activity are a self-expression of the individual, self-control, self-relies on the fundamental needs of realizing their potential".

Usually, games have their own rules, fixed time, and competitive nature. Pupils try to make their team the winner and show their abilities to the fullest. The wide use of interactive methods in the teaching of any subject is becoming a basic need in the current educational system. The term interactive means that the communication during the lesson takes place not only between the student and the teacher, but also between the student and the student, and between the teacher and the student³.

Unconventional teaching requires exactly that. This kind of communication forms students' self-confidence, motivation, and self-expression qualities. Interactive methods combine several goals in the training process, but these methods rely on one criterion: if the studied material is not used in practice, the expected effect cannot be achieved⁴. Interactively teaching a foreign language requires the teacher to organize the lesson process with various activities so that the student learns to speak a foreign language not by reading

² Daminov N.K. Importance of using didactic games in foreign language classes. Communicative aspects of modern linguistics and linguodidactics. - Samarkand: SamDChTI, 2016. -B. 210-211

³ Muhammadiyeva Sh. A. Lesson Planning for Beginners: 5 Tactics for Perfect Preparation Modern Linguistic Research and Didactic Teaching of Foreign Languages. - Samarkand: SamDChTI, 2017. - P.243-244

⁴ Azizkhoyev N.N. Pedagogical technologies and pedagogical skills. -Tashkent: UzYU Literary Fund Publishing House, 2006. - B.91.

and learning, but by using it in practice. occupies in this type of method, the teacher performs the roles of assistant, manager, observer, source of information, and researcher.

Oxford R. likens the relationship between the teacher and the student to a decorative fabric. According to him, just as the matching of threads ensures the beauty and strength of the fabric, excellent results can be expected only if the teaching method of the teacher matches the student. Currently, the main requirement of the teacher is to teach, knowing the student's ability to accept it⁵. Based on the views of scientists in the process of foreign language formation in young students, we can conclude that games and interesting processes during the lesson cause children to develop and develop lexical and grammatical skills without their knowledge. This requires the teacher to have advanced experience and modern knowledge.

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